

*“Let him that has ears to listen listen.”
Jesus’s seven speeches and six pauses in Mark 4:1–32*

ABSTRACT

Jesus’s seven speeches in Mark 4:1–32 progress from the responsibility of the individual Christian to receive the seed, the word, and nurture it well, to showing that as the Christian applied what he heard, God would progressively assist. Jesus ended with the reward—all Jesus’s followers who listening carefully and responded actively would find their home in God’s kingdom. Pauses allow an audience to listen more attentively by building anticipation to then giving the audience time to reflect.

Mark 4:9

καὶ ἔλεγεν ὃς ἔχει ὦτα ἀκούειν ἀκουέτω

Luke 8:8

καὶ ἕτερον ἔπεσεν εἰς τὴν γῆν τὴν ἀγαθὴν καὶ φυὴν ἐποίησεν καρπὸν ἑκατονταπλασίονα ταῦτα λέγων ἐφώνει ὁ ἔχων ὦτα ἀκούειν ἀκουέτω

MATTHEW 13

“Look!

A sower went out to sow;

4 and as he was sowing, some

[seeds] fell alongside the road,

and the birds

came and ate them up.

5 Others

fell upon the rocky places where they

MARK 4

Look!

The sower went out to sow.

4 And as he was sowing, some

[seed] fell alongside the road,

and the birds

came and ate it up.

5 And

other [seed] fell upon the rocky place where it, of course,

LUKE 8

5 “A sower went out to sow his seed.

Well, as he was sowing, some of it fell alongside the road and was trampled down, and the birds of heaven

ate it up.

6 Some other

landed upon the rock-mass,

A S T U D Y I N S I L E N C E

did not have much soil,
and

at once

they
sprang up
because of not having depth of soil. 6 But
when the sun rose
they
were
scorched, and
because
of
not having
root
they
withered.

7 Others,

too,
fell among the thorns, and the thorns

came
up

and
choked
them.

8 Still

others
fell upon the
fine
soil and

they
began
to yield
fruit,

..... this one a hundredfold, that one sixty, the
other thirty.

9 Let him that has ears

listen.”
¶10 So

the disciples
came up and
said to him: “Why is it you speak to them
by the use of illustrations?”

did not have much soil,
and
it
immediately

sprang up
because of not having depth of soil. 6 But
when the sun rose,
it
was
scorched, and
for

not having
root
it
withered.
7 And

other
[seed]

fell among the thorns, and the thorns

came
up

and
choked
it,

and it yielded no fruit.
8 But

others
fell upon the
fine
soil, and,
coming up
and increasing,
they
began
to yield
fruit,
and
they were bearing thirtyfold, and sixty
and a hundred.”
9 So

he
added the word:
“Let him that has ears
to listen
listen.”
¶10 Now
when he got to be alone,
those around him with the twelve

began questioning him on the illustrations.

and,

after

sprouting,

*because
of
not having
moisture
it
dried up

7 Some
other

fell among the thorns, and the thorns
that
grew
up
with it

choked
it
off.

8 Some
other
fell upon the
good
soil, and,
after sprouting,

it

produced
fruit

..... a hundredfold.”
8 As
he told these things,
he
proceeded to call out:
“Let him that has ears
to listen,
listen.”
¶9 But

his disciples

began to ask him what this illustration
might mean.

*Actual order:
“it dried up
because of not having moisture.”

This is the first of Jesus's six pauses in Mark 4:1–32. When we get to the end of the comments on the final pause in verse 30 we will review the sequence of seven speeches punctuated by six pauses.

The theme of Jesus's teaching in this passage is not just listening, but listening carefully with a view to do something with what one hears.

In the Hebrew Scriptures the thought of obedience is expressed by *sha·ma'*, meaning, basically, “hear” or “listen.” Thus, at times *sha·ma'* refers to simple hearing, becoming aware of something through the auditory senses. (Ge 3:10; 21:26; 34:5) But when what is spoken expresses will, desire, instruction, or command, then the sense of the Hebrew term is that of paying heed to or obeying the one speaking. Adam “listened” to his wife's voice, that is, acceded to her desire that he join her in eating the forbidden fruit. (Ge 3:17; compare 21:12.) Joseph refused to “listen” to the importunities of Potiphar's wife. (Ge 39:10) King Saul feared the people and “so obeyed [listened to] their voice,” overstepping God's order in doing so. (1Sa 15:24). (*Insight*, vol. 2, p. 520.)

Jesus wanted his followers to share the Bible's message with others. In this parable, Jesus explained that the seed is the word of God. It is the best good news that anyone could hear—it satisfies every desire, it answers every question; the kingdom that Jesus advertised will solve every problem, and, it is a promise that is verifiably trustworthy and reliable.

Surprisingly, not everyone wants this good news of the kingdom. The disciples had come to know that Jesus was God's own Son, he was the wisest, the most loving person ever to walk the Earth—there was ample proof in his words, in his deeds, in his manner. And yet, the doors of the synagogues being closed to him; many came to hear him but few were changed. Jesus gave a parable to help them and us continue to broadcast the good news of the kingdom even though this news often meets with people who do not want to listen. Ryken (pp. 68, 69) says that in the parable

the main organizing principle is...threefold repetition. Further symmetry stems from the way in which the three unsatisfactory soils are balanced by three degrees of success in the fertile soil. An element

of plot conflict is provided by the environment of struggle in which the seeds play out their destiny—an environment in which seeds are devoured and choked and scorched. The situation of entrusting seed to the earth also possesses the quality of an archetypal risk whose outcome is uncertain and therefore suspenseful.

Insight (vol. 1, p. 1178) has this to say:

There are no clues to the interpretation in the illustration itself, but the explanation is plainly given at Matthew 13:18-23; Mark 4:14-20; and Luke 8:11-15. Attention is focused on the circumstances affecting the soil, or heart, and the influences that can hinder the growth of the seed, or the word of the Kingdom.

Ryken continues:

The parable was a challenge to those who were listening to the claims of the gospel to respond adequately to the message of the kingdom. Jesus delineates three inadequate responses to the message of the kingdom. The parable is thus a warning to the hearers of the gospel to avoid these errors. The harvest produced by the seed that fell in the fertile soil indicates an opportunity to choose a better way.

Nonetheless, since the audience was not just Jesus's disciples, Ryken sees the focus of the parable "on the soils, that is, the hearers of the gospel. *This is a parable about how we listen*, not about how we preach" (Italics ours).

This focus is made more forcible by Jesus's first pause.

Mark's account says, "So he added the word: 'Let him that has ears to listen listen', whereas Luke's account tells us more: "As he told these things, he proceeded to call out: "Let him that has ears to listen, listen". The notable difference is Luke's addition of the word ἐφώνει. NW translates ἐφώνει, "he proceeded to call out", Burnside, "he cried aloud", Robertson, "In a loud voice".

Another difference is between Mark's ὃς ἔχει, "who is having" (*Int*) and Luke's ὁ ἔχων, "the (one) having" (*Int*). Mark's is the relative pronoun plus the present participle, nominative masculine singular. This describes a class of people in general, without picturing one in front of you. It has the feel of a maxim or proverb. Luke's however has *the definite article* plus the present participle, nominative masculine singular. This combination of the definite article with

the participle makes the participle a substantive. This construction emphasises specificity: “the one who has ears,” not just a general “whoever has ears”. In effect, Jesus singled out an individual—“the person who has ears, let that one hear”. It is sharper, more pointed, not proverbial.

In Mark’s account, Jesus ended the parable with the same exhortation—the imperative, ακούετε, “listen!”, which Swete says was “a solemn call to attention”. EGT calls Jesus’s words a summons to reflection implying that understanding is possible for all and therefore obedience is possible for all. Ragg calls Jesus’s call “a penetrating call, appealing for attention and receptiveness”. In fact Trites says the words are “calling for response and appropriate action”. His exhortation amounts to saying, hearing is not the same as understanding.

Through the prophet Jeremiah (5:21, NIV), Jehovah* had told Judah:

Hear this, you foolish and senseless people,
Who have eyes but do not see,
Who have ears but do not hear.

At times, we all hear things without responding. In fact such filtering is essential. But when God speaks, selective listening would have adverse consequences. To treat it as background noise would be to refuse the harvest. By his loud call, Jesus is rousing his audience, he is getting the attention of “very great crowd gathered near him” (Mark 4:1). And in that loud call we can feel Jesus’s anguish that so many who were capable of benefiting would decide that his parable was filtered out. And we can sense his urgency. No one knows how long they have to make such an eternal decision (Mark 13:32, 33).

Jesus uses this same summons, “Let him that has ears to listen, listen”, on a number of occasions (Matthew 11:15; 13:43; Mark 4:9, 23; 7:16; Luke 14:35; Revelation 2:7, 11, 17, 29; 3:6, 13, 22; 13:9). Bailey (p. 155) shows that “a significant number of the major parables have wisdom sayings attached to their conclusions (*cf.* Luke 8:8; 12:21, 48; 16:8b; 18:8b; 19:26)”.

What can be said concerning this particular pause between the parable and the exhortation? The pause allowed the parable time to sink in, especially the results of the fine soil. *Benefit* noted:

*See Appendix.

A pause gives the audience opportunity to reflect on what has just been said, or it creates expectancy for what is to follow. These are not the same. Decide which is the appropriate method to use. But keep in mind that pauses for emphasis should be limited to truly significant statements.

If a speaker pauses the audience will pay closer attention; the audience will become quiet. Perhaps Jesus noticed some or many not paying attention. That pause would have caused them to look at him and concentrate on his appeal.

The pause also made the parable an enacted parable. By pausing and leaving the parable's import unexplained, Jesus was in effect scattering seed in front of his listeners. Their response to the pause would show which kind of "soil" they were. He was allowing the seed to lie there for a moment to see if it would germinate and take root. Jesus gave his audience space for self-examination. It was a moment that pushed his hearers to decide whether they were satisfied with a nice story or whether they would seek the relevance. Luke's imperfect ἐφώνει, "he cried aloud", was full of emotion, and combined with the precision of ὁ ἔχων, it feels like, "You who has ears, listen!" The invitation to each one was, "Do I really want to understand?" And those who wanted to understand immediately approached Jesus (verse 10). Jesus explained to them that the parables functioned as a sieve, separating people—those who were humble from those whose hearts were hardened.

"The options are the same today as they were in Jesus' day. The choices with which Jesus confronted his first listeners are the same ones that he puts before people today" (Ryken).

In conclusion, the pause followed by the loud appeal create a window into Jesus's emotions—his urgency, his anguish and his love.

Mark 4:13

καὶ λέγει αὐτοῖς οὐκ οἶδατε τὴν παραβολὴν ταύτην καὶ πῶς πάσας τὰς παραβολὰς γνῶσεσθε

MATTHEW 13

¶10 So

the disciples
came up and

..... said to him: "Why is it you speak to them
..... by the use of illustrations?"

11 In reply

he

said:

"To you
it is granted to understand
the sacred
secrets
of the kingdom of
the heavens,

but
to
those people
it
is not granted.

12 For whoever has, more will be given
him and he will be made to abound; but
whoever does not have, even what he has
will be taken from him. 13 This is why I
speak to them by the use of illustrations,
because,

looking, they

look in vain,
and

hearing, they

..... hear in vain, neither do they get the
..... sense of it;

14 and toward them the prophecy of Isaiah is
having fulfillment, which says, 'By hearing,
you will hear but by no means get the sense
of it; and, looking, you will look but by no
means see. 15 For the heart of this people
has grown unreceptive, and with their ears
they have heard without response, and they

MARK 4

¶10 Now

when he got to be alone,
those around him with the twelve

..... began questioning him on the illustrations.

11 And

he

proceeded
to say
to them:

"To you

the sacred
secret
of the kingdom of
God
has been given,

but
to
those outside
all things
occur in illustrations,

12 in order that,

though
looking, they

may
look and yet not see,
and,

though
hearing, they

..... may hear and yet not get the sense of it,

..... nor ever turn back and forgiveness be
given them."

LUKE 8

¶9 But

his disciples

..... began to ask him what this illustration
..... might mean.

10 He

said:

"To you
it is granted to understand
the sacred
secrets
of the kingdom of
God,

but
for
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it
is in illustrations,

in order that,

though
looking, they

may
look in vain
and,

though
hearing, they

..... may not get the meaning.

have shut their eyes; that they might never see with their eyes and hear with their ears and get the sense of it with their hearts and turn back, and I heal them.’ ¶16 “However, happy are your eyes because they behold, and your ears because they hear. 17 For I truly say to you, Many prophets and righteous men desired to see the things you are beholding and did not see them, and to hear the things you are hearing and did not hear them.

¶18 “You, then, listen to the illustration of the man that sowed.

13 Further, he said to them: “You do not know this illustration, and so how will you understand all the other illustrations?”

The disciples had approached Jesus to understand the parable. He told them that the parables both reveal and conceal. There would be two responses to his parables: those who wanted to understand and those who did not. “To you the sacred secret of the Kingdom of God has been given, but to those outside all things are in illustrations” (Mark 4:11), in other words, *you* will understand, but for others the illustrations will remain as illustrations—stories without the meaning. As a result those who did not want to understand intended to avoid the greater responsibility that comes with understanding (*w* 1980:6:15:13). Jesus then quoted Jehovah’s words when he commissioned Isaiah to be his prophet. Isaiah was to go to his people and tell them the truth over and over again. But Jehovah told him that the majority would be stubborn and unresponsive, as if they were blind and deaf—shutting their minds and hearts to Isaiah’s message (*ip* vol. 1, p.95, 96). “Though looking, they may look and yet not see, and, though hearing, they may hear and yet not get the sense of it, nor ever turn back and forgiveness be given them” (Mark 4:12).

If we read this, hearing not a tone of bitter exasperation, but a tone of regretful love, it will sound quite different. It will tell us not of a God who deliberately blinded men and hid his truth, but of men who were so dully uncomprehending that it seemed no use even for God to try to penetrate the iron curtain of their lazy incomprehension (Barclay, p. 94).

At this point, according to Matthew’s account, Jesus quoted his Father’s words to

Isaiah more fully. Then, in verse 16, by contrast Jesus told his followers: “Happy are YOUR eyes because they behold, and YOUR ears because they hear”.

Jesus’s pause at the beginning of Mark 4:13 would seem to follow. If that is the case then there appears to be a dissonance between Jesus’s blessing that they can understand and his question that follows the pause: “YOU do not know this illustration, and so how will YOU understand all the other illustrations?”

Was Jesus expressing surprise that they cannot work the meaning out? Was Jesus rebuking them? Was he claiming they were obtuse?

Actually, if we harmonise the two accounts we see that they are complimentary. Jesus’s blessing in Matthew informed his disciples that since they had shown an eagerness to understand, they would have the privilege of comprehension, it would be a divine gift not an intellectual prize. Therefore, Jesus’s question in Mark could be interpreted as a challenge, a summons encouraging them to take the responsibility to work in harmony with this privilege—“Keep on seeking, and YOU will find” (Matthew 7:7)—put the effort in and you *will* understand; you have been granted the key—now use it to open the door. As they listened to Jesus’s explanation of the parable of the sower with an open heart they would know that they were ‘insiders’ (Mark 4:11).

So why the pause?

According to the sequence of events set out in the parallel texts above the pause came after Jesus’s words in Matthew 13:17: “For I truly say to YOU, Many prophets and righteous men desired to see the things YOU are beholding and did not see them, and to hear the things YOU are hearing and did not hear them”.

Jesus had declared the disciples blessed beyond all those in the past who had yearned to see the arrival of the Messiah and the revelation of the sacred secret of the Kingdom. If the pause came after this, it was a silence of wonder—a moment to allow the realisation that they were standing where David, Isaiah, Jeremiah and so many others had yearned to stand.

The pause would also mark a pivot between the inability of all those righteous men to see and hear, and the ability of Jesus’s disciples to see and hear: “YOU, then [οὐὐν], listen to the illustration of the man that sowed” (verse 18). The conjunction οὐὐν highlights the pivot.

However, what if the pause came after Jesus’s words in Mark 4:12 where he was

referencing Isaiah 6:9, 10: “Though looking, they may look and yet not see, and, though hearing, they may hear and yet not get the sense of it, nor ever turn back and forgiveness be given them”.

Jesus’s silence allowed for his disciples to reflect seriously on whether they would ‘look and not see, hear and not get the sense’. The pause was a shift from the past to the present, to that very moment when the disciples stood in front of Jesus—will you be like those in the past or will you be different? Will you slip back or will you seize the gift of the “the sacred secret of the Kingdom of God”? Will you allow the seed to be taken or allow it to sink deep into the soil? In effect, Jesus was saying, You are not meant to be blind like them, but you must be awake to the danger. The silence after the quotation functioned as a threshold on which hearing stopped and the disciples had to decide whether to resist or receive understanding; it allowed the disciples to realise what is so often sadly the case—divine truths can pass many by even while they are listening to them.

Mark 4:21

καὶ ἔλεγεν αὐτοῖς ὅτι μήτι ἔρχεται ὁ λύχνος ἵνα ὑπὸ τὸν μῶδιον τεθῆῃ ἢ ὑπὸ τὴν κλίνην οὐχ ἵνα ἐπὶ τὴν λυχνίαν τεθῆῃ

If we look at the parallel account in Matthew we see that in between the parable of the sower and the parable of the lampstand Jesus relates the parable of the wheat and the weeds (13:24–30), the mustard grain and the leaven (31–33), he says that his use of parables fulfil prophecy (34, 35), he explains the parable of the wheat and the weeds (36–43), followed by relating the parable of the hidden treasure, the fine pearl and the dragnet (44–50). So the pause in Mark’s account was probably acknowledging this.

However, if we isolate Mark we see that the pause played a role in the conversation. In Mark’s account the focus is not on the sower—sowing liberally—but on the soils—listening carefully.

The disciples had asked Jesus for an explanation of the parable of the sower. He then told them that there would be two responses to his parables: those who wanted to understand and those who did not (4:11). Again he appealed to his disciples to pay attention to how they listened. Then he explained the metaphors of the sower, the seed and the soils—a parable all about listening and responding. Then he paused. Then he said:

21 A lamp is not brought to be put under a measuring basket or under a bed, is it? It is brought to be put upon a lampstand, is it not? 22 For there is nothing hidden except for the purpose of being exposed; nothing has become carefully concealed but for the purpose of coming into the open. 23 Whoever has ears to listen, let him listen.

By carefully explaining the parable, Jesus showed that he wanted people to understand. Now you understand, what will you do about this? His two rhetorical questions in verse 21 were meant to provoke thought, to provoke his audience to listen carefully. The absurd image of hiding a lamp under a basket or bed emphasized that he was not using parables to obfuscate, but his teachings were meant to be understood by those who wanted to. The inability to understand by some was not Jesus’s fault—he had lit a lamp and put it on a *lampstand* and he was now endeavouring to help all who wanted to understand. And, when they understood, to do something with it.

So if we just focus on the Mark account, this pause seems to be part of Jesus's attempt to help his audience to listen carefully. Undoubtedly, a speaker who pauses allows the audience to listen in a more considered way, it allows for a opportunity for the audience to engage more deeply. As Barclay wrote: "Jesus did not wish to save men the mental sweat of thinking; he wished to make them think. He did not wish to make their minds lazy; he wished to make them active" (p. 87).

Mark 4:24

καὶ ἔλεγεν αὐτοῖς βλέπετε τί ἀκούετε ἐν ᾧ μέτρῳ μετρεῖτε μετρηθήσεται ὑμῖν καὶ προστεθήσεται ὑμῖν

Jesus had concluded the parable of the sower with an exhortation: ὃς ἔχει ὦτα ἀκούειν ἀκουέτω, “Let him that has ears to listen listen” (Mark 4:9). This is emphasised by Jesus reiterating his exhortation in verse 23: εἴ τις ἔχει ὦτα ἀκούειν ἀκουέτω, “Whoever has ears to listen, let him listen”. The difference between the phrases is in the introduction—the first has a relative clause ὃς, the second a conditional, εἴ τις. ὃς, “Let him”, emphasises the *availability* of the understanding to those open to it, εἴ τις, “Whoever”, narrows the appeal and stresses the *responsibility* that follows understanding—‘If you have ears, then use them!’ Jesus wanted his disciples to not just hear but understand and then respond.

After this Jesus paused. Then he said:

24 Pay attention to what YOU are hearing. With the measure that YOU are measuring out, YOU will have it measured out to YOU, yes, YOU will have more added to YOU. 25 For he that has will have more given to him; but he that does not have, even what he has will be taken away from him.

“Pay attention” Jesus said. The word is βλέπετε, which is the present active imperative, second person plural, of βλέπω, literally “see”, “look” or “watch”. However, the verb often functions idiomatically to mean “be careful”, “take heed” or “pay attention”. It is not about visualisation, here it is used to foreground the need for mental alertness and discernment (*cf.* Mark 13:9; 1 Corinthians 10:12).

The juxtaposition of βλέπετε τί ἀκούετε—‘see’, ‘hear’—highlights active perception not passive reception. It is as if Jesus said, be careful *how* you take in what you hear; weigh it all discerningly. In this chapter, Jesus was urging attentive evaluation of what they were being taught—don’t let the seed fall on the compacted soil alongside the road, but welcome it into fine soil, then nurture it, allow it to take root, develop, grow and produce fruit (verses 4, 8).

By way of an incentive he went on to say: “With the measure that YOU are measuring out, YOU will have it measured out to YOU, yes, YOU will have more added to YOU”. In other words, the measure of undivided attention and active thought and determination and diligence that they would give to Jesus’s teachings

would determine their growth and future blessings—“For he that has will have more given to him”. But the reverse side is the terrible fact of atrophy—the atrophy of every power or capacity that is *not* used—“he that does not have, even what he has will be taken away from him”. Those who use neither their ears nor their will, lose their power to hear and to put those ideas into practice. And inevitably, even what they have will be taken away. The result? The dimming of spiritual insight, the paralysis of conscience, the clouding of one’s vision of God, the loss of his support (*Interpreter’s*, vol. 7, p. 703). The servant who did nothing with his talent was told, “For to everyone that has, more will be given and he will have abundance; but as for him that does not have, even what he has will be taken away from him” (Matthew 25:29).

So, why did Jesus pause between what he said in verse 23 and verse 24? After saying, “Whoever has ears to listen, let him listen”, the pause may have been to let the imperative sink in—once we have heard then there is responsibility to do. Was he giving his audience time to listen to their personal response? A pause allows an audience to hear their thoughts and how they plan to react.

The pause also created anticipation for what he was about to say. In this case, a parable that stressed a consistent habit of listening carefully, then applying what is learnt, then growing spiritually.

Mark 4:26

καὶ ἔλεγεν οὕτως ἐστὶν ἡ βασιλεία τοῦ θεοῦ ὡς ἄνθρωπος βάλῃ τὸν σπόρον ἐπὶ τῆς γῆς

The parable that follows this pause is usually seen as a lesson in being regular in sowing seed—the word of God. Then, over time, enjoying the results—making disciples. However, if this parable is related to the context—how we listen—then there might possibly be another interpretation.

26 In this way the kingdom of God is just as when a man casts the seed upon the ground, 27 and he sleeps at night and rises up by day, and the seed sprouts and grows tall, just how he does not know. 28 Of its own self the ground bears fruit gradually, first the grass-blade, then the stalk head, finally the full grain in the head. 29 But as soon as the fruit permits it, he thrusts in the sickle, because the harvesttime has come.

The phrase οὕτως ἐστὶν, translated “in this way”, forms a link with verse 25: “For he that has will have more given to him; but he that does not have, even what he has will be taken away from him”. The man *has* to cast the seed—‘what he has’—upon the ground so that ‘more can be given to him’, otherwise the seed will remain just a seed and nothing will result—all that potential will *not* be realised, so ‘will be taken away from him’.

Reference to the kingdom of God in the introduction suggests that this is further incentive for Jesus’s disciples to listen carefully, because if they did, entry into the kingdom would be possible (*cf.* verse 24).

In this parable there is an obvious collaboration between the sower and the unseen power at work in the soil. The sower initiates the work, but then has to patiently wait for the soil to play its part before he can act once more and benefit. Here is a suggestion: if the disciples diligently listened and applied what they learnt, then God would do his part to help them grow spiritually, resulting in a fruitful Christian and entry into the kingdom of God—the harvesttime.

Swete calls this parable the “Parable of the Automatic Action of the Soil”. He chose the word “automatic” because the first word in verse 28 is αὐτομάτη, translated “of its own self”. If there is any truth in our proposed interpretation, then Jesus is saying that when the disciples are assiduous in applying what they learn, then God will automatically support their efforts and they will gain entry

into his kingdom. That is really encouraging—there are certain things that a Christian does that spontaneously and inevitably makes God act automatically.

Why did Jesus pause?

He had just said: “For he that has will have more given to him; but he that does not have, even what he has will be taken away from him”. This is quite some warning—spiritual receptivity is not neutral—it grows or it shrinks. A pause after that line allows the weight of the statement to settle. It is the kind of statement that could well have silenced the disciples. And perhaps Jesus allowed the disciples to ask for further clarification.

After the severity of “even what he has will be taken away from him”, Jesus moved to this quiet parable of almost effortless growth—sowing then resting while the soil does its work. That shift probably required a breathing space ahead of Jesus’s reassuring promise that God would join forces with them to assist them to reach their goal. Verses 24 and 25 stressed human responsibility in listening; verses 26 to 29 stressed God’s quiet support.

Mark 4:30

καὶ ἔλεγεν πῶς ὁμοιώσωμεν τὴν βασιλείαν τοῦ θεοῦ ἢ ἐν τίνι αὐτὴν παραβολῇ θῶμεν

The final parable in the sequence is the culmination of Jesus’s instructions to his disciples to listen meticulously and commit to what they have learnt.

30 And he went on to say: “With what are we to liken the kingdom of God, or in what illustration shall we set it out? 31 Like a mustard grain, which at the time it was sown in the ground was the tiniest of all the seeds that are on the earth— 32 but when it has been sown, it comes up and becomes greater than all other vegetables and produces great branches, so that the birds of the heaven are able to find lodging under its shadow.

By ending a parable and then pausing, Jesus created a moment of anticipation. When he then asked, “With what can we compare the Kingdom of God?”, the audience leans in.

In the Garden of Eden, Adam knew what was good—eating to satisfaction from all the fruit trees of the garden—and what was bad—not eating from one particular tree. So the knowledge of good and bad was more than just knowing what was good and bad, it was “the power of deciding for himself what is good and what is evil and of acting accordingly, a claim to complete moral independence... The first sin was an attack on God’s sovereignty” (JB).

The tree was in effect God’s flag—planted in his territory showing that he was the sovereign. The fruit tree was a perfect representation of God’s loving rulership. God used a fruit tree to represent his kingdom when he gave a vision to Nebuchadnezzar. Recounting the vision, Nebuchadnezzar said that this “tree grew and became strong, and its top reached the heavens, and it was visible to the ends of the whole earth. Its foliage was beautiful, and its fruit was abundant, and there was food on it for all. Beneath it the beasts of the field would seek shade, and on its branches the birds of the heavens would dwell, and all creatures would feed from it” (Daniel 4:11, 12).

This tells us that God’s sovereignty will be earthwide, that it will give food and shelter to all who come under its jurisdiction—no one will lack. This is a dominion that would attract many in every part of the Earth who would happily dwell in subjection to his sovereignty and in unity with others who have accepted God’s

right to decide on what is good and what is bad. After all, a bird is free to fly and dwell on another tree; an animal can wander off to shelter elsewhere.

Here in Mark 4, the tiny mustard seed grows into a λάχανον which is a vegetable plant. Jesus likened God's sovereignty to a large treelike plant where its subjects willingly "find lodging under its shadow". This would be the ultimate reward for the disciples if they obeyed Jesus's command: "Let him that has ears to listen listen" (verse 9). They would enter a supranational community living under God's sovereignty.

Why did Jesus pause before his final parable about listening?

The penultimate parable brought in the role of God in helping the disciples to grow and attain their eternal goal. The final parable gave them a picture of that future—from a very small beginning, the kingdom of God would grow and grow in adherents and the kingdom would eventually take back control over the Earth (Isaiah 9:7; Matthew 6:10).

The pause allowed for the comforting and invigorating news of God's assistance to sink in. It also kept the two seed and plant parables separate.

These seven short speeches with six pauses show Jesus's pedagogy, how he guides those who were willing across thresholds and into new spaces of insight.

In this passage there are five parables: the sower and the soils, the lamp and its locations, the measure, the sower and the soil, the mustard grain's transformation into a tree. With these five parables Jesus took his audience on a journey of revelation up a series of steps, while at the same time urging them to keep listening and to reap the rewards.

Although the parables are connected with this theme, each parable is a world of its own. For example, the birds in the first and last parables are not symbols of the same thing. The first birds, Jesus said, represented Satan; the last represented Jesus's followers. So each parable needs to be decoded separately. As a consequence, we cannot assume that the sower and the seed correspond to the same things in each of the parables. In the first, the sower represents the person sharing the good news of the kingdom—the seed (*cf.* Luke 4:43). In the second, the sower represents the individual Christian endeavouring to get into the kingdom; the seed, we suggested, represented what the Christian heard and what

he did with what he heard, in this case—he planted it. In the third, the sower is not specified, but Jesus said the kingdom of God is “like a mustard grain, which at the time it was sown in the ground was the tiniest of all the seeds that are on the earth” (verse 31). This would mean that the sower is God who established the kingdom in order to rescue mankind; the seed is the kingdom. Because each parable is a world in itself the pauses played an important partitioning role.

We have shown that the theme of Jesus’s speeches was listening. Various forms of listening have been identified. Passmore and Oades list a number. Amongst those were passive listening—you hear the words but you are not fully paying attention, your mind may wander and you retain little; selective listening—you listen only for what interests you or stands out, much of the speaker’s meaning is missed; active listening—you pay deliberate attention, take in the content and may ask clarifying question; reflective listening—you listen carefully and reflect on how you will respond and what you will do, you are engaged. By his series of speeches Jesus was entreating his disciples to actively listen and then reflect on how they ought to react.

Looking back, Jesus started with the responsibility of the individual Christian to receive the seed and nurture it well. He encouraged the disciples to listen actively and to take the initiative and play their part. As Jesus progressed, he showed that as the Christian applied what he heard, God would progressively assist. Jesus ended with the climax—all Jesus’s followers rewarded for listening carefully and responding actively by finding their home in God’s kingdom.

ABBREVIATIONS AND BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Bible quotations are from the *New World Translation of the Holy Scriptures, with References*, 1984, unless otherwise indicated.

The Introduction to this edition of NW contains this explanation:

Where “you” is printed in small capital letters, it shows that the pronoun is plural. Also, where the plural number of a verb is not apparent, its plurality is indicated by printing it in small capital letters. If the context already clearly indicates plurality, then no special capitalization is used.

APPENDIX

In the Bible the divine name יהוה occurs almost seven thousand times, more often than any of God's titles, and more often than any other separate Hebrew word.

There are many theophoric names in the Bible. The majority of Bible translators transliterate those names which have the first two syllables of the divine name as Jeho. Hence: Jehonathan, Jehoshua, Jehoshaphat, Jehoahaz, Jehonadab, Jehoram etc. When the Israelites shortened a name they would not abbreviate but they contracted it by removing syllables from the middle of the name. So Jehonathan was reduced to Jonathan; Jehoshua became Joshua; Jehonadab became Jonadab. God's name was contracted to Jah, hence: Elijah, Abijah and Hallelujah etc. Therefore, the divine name must have had three syllables, not two.

We believe that a י is more likely to be transliterated as a y in English, and a ו is more likely to be transliterated as a w. So the divine name could be *Yehowah*. However, most Bible scholars avoid any transliteration. They use the tetragrammaton in Hebrew letters יהוה, or they display the divine name as YHWH. This is all well and good, but it is inconsistent with their transliteration of other Bible names. If they are to be consistent then they should either use Yehonathan for Jonathan or show the Hebrew letters יהנתן, or YWNTN. Sometimes they use *Yahweh* which disregards how names were shortened, and it only has two syllables.

The argument that the vowels of יהוה are those of אֱלֹהֵינוּ does not hold up because the vowels are not the same.

Gesenius pointed out that "Those who consider that יהוה was the actual pronunciation [of God's name] are not altogether without ground on which to defend their opinion. In this way can the abbreviated syllables יהו and יו, with which many proper names begin, be more satisfactorily explained."

We believe that *Jehovah* is a reasonable transliteration of the tetragrammaton.